

ENEXA: Efficient Explainable Learning on Knowledge Graphs

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Abstract

The ENEXA project builds upon results in knowledge representation and machine learning to develop scalable, transparent, and explainable hybrid machine learning algorithms that combine symbolic and sub-symbolic learning. The project focuses on knowledge graphs with rich semantics as knowledge representation mechanism because of their increasing popularity across domains and industries. Some explainable and transparent machine learning approaches for knowledge graphs are known to already provide guarantees with respect to their completeness and correctness. However, they are still impossible or impractical to deploy on real-world data due to the scale, incompleteness and inconsistency of knowledge graphs in the wild. ENEXA has devised new machine learning approaches that maintain formal guarantees pertaining to completeness and correctness while exploiting different representations (formal logics, embeddings and tensors) of knowledge graphs in a concurrent fashion. With these new methods, the project has advanced the scalability of machine learning, especially on knowledge graphs. A key innovation of ENEXA lies in its approach to explainability. Here, we focus on devising human-centred explainability techniques based on the concept of co-construction, where human and machine enter a conversation to co-construct human-understandable explanations. The resulting approach is deployed in three sectors of European significance, i.e., business services, geospatial intelligence and brand marketing.

Keywords

Explainable AI, Knowledge Graphs, Human-centered Machine Learning, Trustworthy AI, Hybrid Approaches

1. Project information

- Project short name/acronym: ENEXA
- Project full name: Efficient Explainable Learning on Knowledge Graphs
- Project website link: <https://enexa.eu/>
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- Project partners: Universitaet Paderborn (UPB); National Center for Scientific Research “Demokritos” (NCSR-D); European Union Satellite Centre (SATCEN); DATEV EG (DATEV); Universiteit van Amsterdam (UvA); Weblyzard Technology GmbH (WLT)
- Project logo: [link to enexa logo](#)
- Project video: Explainable machine learning using knowledge graphs extracted from Wikipedia by Axel Ngonga at [link](#).

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2. Project summary

Knowledge graphs have emerged as fundamental data structures powering an increasing number of user-facing applications while serving as critical enablers for explainable machine learning. Despite their growing importance, real-world knowledge graphs present significant challenges that hinder their full potential. The inherent scale of web-level knowledge graphs makes them difficult to store and query efficiently, particularly when executing complex analytical queries needed to extract high-value insights. Furthermore, their frequent inconsistencies cause standard inference engines to fail, while their incompleteness leaves downstream applications unaware of potentially crucial assertions. The non-vectorial nature of knowledge graph representations additionally creates barriers for applying classical machine learning techniques effectively.

The ENEXA project addresses these fundamental challenges through novel approaches to knowledge graph extraction, storage, inference, and explainable artificial intelligence. By developing specialized techniques for web-scale knowledge graphs, the project enables reliable machine learning applications while empowering enterprises to build robust data strategies. The work combines advances in knowledge representation with artificial intelligence to create scalable, transparent algorithms that maintain explainability even at large scales. A key innovation involves human-centered explainability techniques based on the principle of co-construction, where systems engage users in collaborative dialogues to produce mutually understandable explanations. This approach recognizes that effective explanations must adapt to users' existing knowledge and allow interactive exploration of the reasoning process.

Three strategically selected use cases in business software services, geospatial intelligence, and data-driven brand communications serve as validation scenarios for ENEXA's techniques. These domains were chosen for their anticipated growth within European data value chains and their representative challenges. In the business software domain, the techniques help explain complex decision processes in enterprise systems. For geospatial intelligence, they enable traceable analysis of interconnected geographical data. In brand communications, they provide auditable explanations for data-driven marketing decisions.

Our most recent work has yielded concrete advances in explanation co-construction, particularly for class expression learning tasks. The developed system employs large language models to verbalize class expressions and engage users in explanatory dialogues (namely "explanation-by-exploration" [1]). Users can interrogate the system about specific class expressions, with the model providing contextual information including the positive and negative examples used during learning and the source knowledge graph elements. This creates a dynamic where users can progressively explore and understand the system's reasoning through natural language interaction. The technical implementation, publicly available [here](#), demonstrates how provenance information and user knowledge can be combined to generate tailored explanations.

Our ongoing work focuses on rigorous evaluation of the explanation quality produced through these co-construction methods while expanding the approach to additional knowledge graph reasoning tasks. The project simultaneously advances the underlying infrastructure for handling web-scale knowledge graphs, developing solutions for their storage, querying, and completion. Together, these contributions move toward making knowledge graphs truly accessible and actionable for both technical and non-technical users across European industry and research institutions. By bridging the gap between symbolic knowledge representations and modern machine learning while maintaining explainability, ENEXA helps realize the promise of knowledge graphs as trustworthy foundations for data-driven decision making.

3. Project available results

The ENEXA project has produced significant outcomes in explainable machine learning over knowledge graphs. Here, we will summarize some key outcomes, including open-source tools, publications, and outreach initiatives. Our open-source libraries for large-scale knowledge graph embeddings (Dice

embeddings (<https://pypi.org/project/dicee/>), OWL ontology creation and manipulation (OWLAPy <https://pypi.org/project/owlapy/>), and structured machine learning tasks by processing knowledge bases, inductive logic programming and ontology engineering (Ontolearn <https://pypi.org/project/ontolearn/>) have collectively surpassed 50,000 downloads, demonstrating widespread adoption in the community. The ENEXA dashboard provides real-time market intelligence by analyzing public discourse about key technologies through knowledge graph-based analysis of content from chip manufacturers NVIDIA, Intel Corporation, and AMD.

Our research contributions include novel approaches to universal knowledge graph embeddings (<https://embeddings.cc/>) [2]. Most knowledge graphs obtain embeddings by learning the structure of a knowledge graph within a link prediction setting. As a result, the embeddings reflect only the structure of a single knowledge graph, and embeddings for different knowledge graphs are not aligned. We instantiate our idea by computing universal embeddings based on DBpedia and Wikidata yielding embeddings for about 180 million entities, 15 thousand relations, and 1.2 billion triples. We also developed temporally robust entity linking methods (CYCLE [3] and TIGER[4]) that address the challenge of performance degradation over constantly evolving knowledge graphs. The AutoCL framework [5] advances interpretable concept learning through automated feature selection and hyperparameter optimization specifically designed for knowledge graphs. These contributions have been presented at major conferences including CIKM, ECAI, and ICAI with accompanying libraries and open-source code.

ENEXA maintains active engagement with the research community through participation in ESWC and ISWC conferences, where our members have presented work on conjunctive query evaluation, entity summarization, and class membership verification. We have also co-organized workshops on the intersection of large language models and knowledge graphs (e.g., *Knowledge Base Construction from Pre-Trained Language Models* at ISWC) and tutored at the *International Semantic Web Research Summer School*, fostering the next generation of researchers in this field. A comprehensive list of publications is available at <https://enexa.eu/publications/>.

4. Relevance to ESWC conference

Knowledge graphs and machine learning are key topics within the ESWC conference. Project outcomes have been published at ESWC [6] including at the 2025 conference. Explainability has also featured at the conference and has been a strong area of interest to the conference.

5. Value brought by the project to ESWC participants

We have a number of open source packages as discussed above that could be very useful to the community. This includes a new scalable triple store - <https://tentris.io>. We also think our new approaches to machine learning and explainability are of interest to the ESWC participants. Lastly, we think our use cases illustrate challenges and potential areas of interest to the conference.

6. Value gained by the project from ESWC participation

The upcoming ESWC Project Networking track presents a strategic opportunity to amplify ENEXA's impact during its final phase. We plan to leverage this platform to showcase our innovations in explainable knowledge graph learning, particularly our co-construction framework and scalable inference techniques, to a targeted audience of researchers and industry partners. This engagement will facilitate critical discussions about the challenges and potentials with peers working on similar topics.

As ENEXA approaches completion, the conference will serve as an ideal venue to explore follow-up collaborations and funding opportunities. We anticipate identifying concrete synergies for Horizon Europe proposals. The networking sessions will also enable knowledge transfer to ongoing initiatives, ensuring ENEXA's results continue to influence emerging standards in explainable AI and Knowledge Graph construction.

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